

Quinazolones. Part VIII*

Syntheses of Some Oxazolo and *iso*-Oxazolo Quinazolones

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Syntheses of 2-methyloxazolo(2,3-b)quinazoline-5(4H)-one (I), 2,3-dihydro-2-methyloxazolo(3,2-c)quinazoline-5(4H)-one (XXII) and 4-allyl-1H,2H-oxazolo(3, 2-a)quinazoline-1,5-(4H)-dione (XXIII) from 3-allylquinazoline-2,4-(1H,3H)-dione (XV) are described.

IN continuation of our studies leading to the formation of tricyclic furo-quinazolones¹⁻⁴, it was envisaged to build an oxazole ring in the pyrimidine part of the quinazolone moiety which has identical position of atoms in one side of the ring. The fusion of the two heterocycles with nitrogen bridgehead can be accomplished at either of the alternative positions 1,2 and 2,3 of a 4-quinazolone system giving rise to four possible isomeric compounds I to IV, where I and III are oxazoloquinazolones and II and IV are *isooxazoloquinazolones*. Any such fusion at the 3,4-position, however, would lead to the formation of either oxazoloquinazoline or oxazoloquinazolin-2(1H)-ones. Some

6(*N*) hydrochloric acid or chloroacetic acid to obtain the key intermediate (VI) led to the recovery of the unchanged starting material (XI). Treatment of the thionoquinazolone (XI) with methyl iodide in dimethyl formamide in the presence of potassium carbonate gave 3-allyl-2-methylthioquinazoline-4(3H)-one (V) which on subsequent hydrolysis with 6(*N*) hydrochloric acid afforded compound (XII) quantitatively. Though the compound is readily soluble in alkali and also undergoes Schotten-Baumann reaction to give a poor yield of the benzoate (IX), unlike the observation of Bhargava and Singh⁷, it was characterised as the dione (XII) not only due to its reluctance to acetylation or its failure to give

I

II

III

IV

synthetic approach to such tricyclic oxazoloquinazolone systems are discussed in this paper. The method of Kaufmann⁵ as adopted by us^{1,2} for building the furan ring was utilized to develop the desired oxazole ring. Accordingly 3-allyl-2-hydroxyquinazolin-4(3H)-one (VI) and 1-allyl-2-hydroxyquinazolin-4(1H)-one (VIII) were selected to be the key intermediates which could be transformed to the respective linear (I) and angular (III) oxazoloquinazolones.

Direct hydrolysis of 3-allyl-2-thionoquinazolin-4(3H, 1H)-one (XI)⁶ in absolute ethanol either with

condensation product with chloroacetic acid but also corroborated by the i.r. spectral data having no band for the hydroxyl group rather a definite N-H peak at 3000 cm⁻¹ as well as two peaks at 1670 and 1750 cm⁻¹ attributed to the respective carbonyl groups at C₍₂₎ and C₍₄₎ and is in keeping with the previous observations⁸. It is further confirmed by its failure to be cyclised as observed by Puar and Co-workers⁹ in similarly situated sulphur analogue XI either with aqueous hydrobromic acid or with bromine in acetic acid. Rather treatment of XII with 48% hydrobromic acid unexpectedly gave 3-(2'-bromopropyl)quinazoline-2,4-(1H, 3H)-dione (XIII) which when refluxed with 5 molar alcoholic potassium hydroxide, instead of giving the cyclised product (XVI) gave 3-(2'-hydroxypropyl) quinazoline-2,4-(1H,

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3H)dione (XIV) as the major product, the latter, however, when refluxed with acetic anhydride could be converted and identified as (XVI), being identical to the same obtained as per reported procedure¹⁰. Subsequent treatment of (XVI) with palladised charcoal though converted it to the desired oxazoloquinazolone (I; R = 2, CH₃), it could also be prepared alternatively from 3-(2', 3'-dibromopropyl)-quinazoline-2,4(1H, 3H)dione (XV) obtained by the bromination of XII with pyridinium-bromide-perbromide only when refluxed with 2 molar alcoholic potassium hydroxide along with a small amount of water insoluble bromine containing compound, m.p. 170°-174°, the structure of which is assigned as

alcoholic alkali during cyclisation is important since its higher concentration leads to the isolation of mixture of products probably with the rupture of the heterocyclic ring whereas the cyclisation of either XIII or XV with potassium carbonate in acetone passes smoothly. The other one step projected route to obtain the linear compound (XVI) by the cyclisation of the dione (XII) with polyphosphoric acid, however did not furnish the expected dihydrocompound XVI, rather an altogether different but isomeric product was isolated quantitatively and is assigned to have the angular structure (XVIII), the only other theoretical possibility. This leads us to conclude that the C₍₁₎ carbonyl group is more

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|---|---|
| XIX | XVIII |
| V : R = SCH ₃ | VII : R ² = SCH ₃ |
| VI : R = OH | VIII : R = OH |
| IX : R = OCOPh | |
| X : R = OCH ₂ COOEt | |
| XI : X = S; R = allyl | XVI : R = CH ₃ |
| XII : X = O; R = allyl | XVII : R = CH ₂ Br |
| XIII : X = O; R = CH ₂ CH(Br)CH ₃ | |
| XIV : X = O; R = CH ₂ CH(OH)CH ₃ | |
| XV : X = O; R = CH ₂ -CH(Br)CH ₂ Br | |

2-bromomethyl-2, 3-dihydrooxazolo(2,3-b)quinazoline-5(4H)-one (XVII). Such formulation is deduced on the basis of the analytical data as well as in analogy with the formation of 2'-bromomethyl-2',3'-dihydro-6-methoxy-2,3-diphenylfuro-(4', 5' : 8, 7) quinazolin-4(3H)-one¹ from 7-acetoxy-8-(2', 3'-dibromopropyl)-6-methoxy-2,3-diphenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one and other similar compounds^{11,12} under identical experimental conditions. In this instance the concentration of the

active than that of C₍₂₎ and is in keeping with the reactivity of similarly substituted halogen atoms¹³. Since both XI and XII are expected to have identical tautomeric nature¹⁴ and our success in converting the former to the thiazolidoquinazolone¹⁵ prompted us to synthesise the remaining angular oxazoloquinazolone (XIX) from the dione (XII) which were at our hand than to investigate the formation of the intermediate (VIII) which has not been reported in

the literature so far. Accordingly when the sodium salt of the dione (XII) was made to react with ethylbromoacetate gave the alkoxy derivative (X), reduction of which with potassium borohydride followed by acid catalysed dehydration led to the isolation of 4-allyl-1H,2H-oxazolo(3,2-a)quinazoline-1,5(4H)dione (XIX).

The above success led us to extend the condensation reaction of the sodium salt of the dione (XII) and its 3-phenyl analogue with phenacylbromide, *p*-bromophenacylbromide, bromoacetone and the results will be published elsewhere.

Experimental

All the m.p.s were determined in open capillaries in H₂SO₄ bath and are uncorrected. Extracts were dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ unless otherwise stated. Light petroleum used had b.p. 60°–80°. PPA used was of BDH laboratory reagent grade.

3-Allyl-2-methylthioquinazoline-4(3H)-one (V): To XI (2.18 g.; 0.01 mole) dissolved in minimum quantity of dry DMF (10 ml.) was treated with methyl iodide (1.56 g.; 0.65 ml; 0.011 mole) and K₂CO₃ (1 g.) added. The mixture was stirred, allowed to stand overnight and poured in ice water when solid separated out. It was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from dilute ethanol to give V as clusters of colourless needles (2.0 g.; 90%), m.p. 84°–85°, ν_{\max} (KBr) 1180, 1340, 1360, 1475, 1560, 1600, 1710 cm⁻¹. λ_{\max} (MeOH) 237, 276 nm. (ϵ_{\max} , 11410, 3005) (Found: C, 62.1; H, 5.0; N, 12.5. C₁₂H₁₂N₂OS requires: C, 62.0; H, 5.2; N, 12.7%).

3-Allylquinazoline-2,4(1H, 3H)-dione (XII): 6(N) HCl (30 ml.) was added to a solution of (V) (3.32 g.; 0.01 mole) in ethanol (20 ml.) and the reaction mixture was heated under reflux for 3 hr., a trap containing NaOH (1.5 g.) connected to the top of the reflux condenser. The resulting solution on cooling deposited elongated colourless needles which were filtered, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol to afford XII as elongated colourless needles (1.8 g.; 90%), m.p. 188°–189°. λ_{\max} (KBr) 1280, 1340, 1465, 1670 (quinazoline carbonyl), 1750 (dione) 3000 cm⁻¹ (broad; > NH; amide). λ_{\max} (MeOH) 230, 310 nm. (ϵ_{\max} , 9202; 3441) (Found: C, 65.4; H, 4.7; N, 13.7. C₁₁H₁₀N₂O₂ requires: C, 65.3; H, 4.9; N, 13.8%), lit.¹³ m.p. 189°.

3-Allyl-2-benzoyloxyquinazoline-4(3H)-one (IX): Solution of XII (2.0 g.; 0.01 mole) in aq. NaOH (10%; 25 ml.) cooled to 0° was treated with benzoyl chloride (1.5 g.; 1.2 ml; 0.011 mole) and stirred vigorously, keeping the reaction mixture in an ice bath all the time, with a special care, not to allow the temperature to rise above 4°. The solid that separated after sometime was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol to furnish IX as rectangular plates (1 g.; 33%), m.p. 170°–171°. ν_{\max} (KBr) 760, 965, 1130, 1275, 1340, 1450, 1500, 1670 and 1710 cm⁻¹. λ_{\max} (MeOH) 223, 310 nm. (ϵ_{\max} , 64565, 22015) (Found: C, 70.7; H, 4.5; N, 9.0. C₁₈H₁₄N₂O₃ requires: C, 70.5; H, 4.6; N, 9.1%).

3-(2'-bromopropyl) quinazoline-2, 4(1H, 3H)-dione (XIII): XII (2.0 g.; 0.01 mole) was refluxed with

48% aq. HBr (30 ml.) for 2 hr. when a clear solution was obtained. The reaction mixture was then cooled, diluted with water and the solid that separated was filtered. The residue was triturated well with aq. NaHCO₃ (5%; 20 ml.) filtered, washed with water and crystallised from methanol to yield XVI as colourless needles (2.0 g.; 70%), m.p. 214°–215°. ν_{\max} (KBr) 765, 1065, 1090, 1265, 1330, 1445, 1650 (C₍₂₎ Carbonyl), 1735 (C₍₄₎ Carbonyl) and 3195 cm⁻¹ (> NH; amide); λ_{\max} (MeOH) 226, 310 nm. (ϵ_{\max} , 19200, 5793) (Found: C, 46.4; H, 3.7; N, 10.00; Br, 28.00. C₁₁H₁₁N₂O₂Br requires: C, 46.6; H, 3.9; N, 9.8; Br, 28.2%).

3-(2', 3'-Dibromopropyl) quinazoline-2, 4(1H, 3H)-dione (XV): To a solution of XII (2.0 g.; 0.01 mole) in glacial ACOH (20 ml.) was treated with pyridiniumbromideperbromide (4 g.; 0.0125 mole) and stirred mechanically at room temperature. After 0.5 hr. the reagent was consumed and it was further stirred for a period of 0.5 hr. by the end of which pale yellow solid separated out. Next day the ice cooled reaction mixture was diluted with ice cold water, filtered, washed with water and crystallised from glacial ACOH to give XV as colourless needles (2.8 g.; 80%), m.p. 217°–218°. ν_{\max} (KBr) 765, 1260, 1320, 1445, 1640 (C₍₄₎ Carbonyl), 1720 (Carbonyl at C₍₄₎). λ_{\max} (EtOH) 232, 310 nm. (ϵ_{\max} , 10733, 4209) (Found: C, 36.6; H, 2.8; N, 7.6; Br, 44.0. C₁₁H₁₀N₂O₂Br₂ requires: C, 36.4; H, 2.7; N, 7.7; Br, 44.2%).

3-(2'-Hydroxypropyl) quinazoline-2,4-(1H, 3H)-dione (XV): XIII (2.83 g.; 0.01 mole) was heated with a solution of KOH (5.6 g.; 0.10 mole) in ethanol (50 ml.) on steam bath for 2 hr., the excess of ethanol (40 ml.) was distilled off, the residual solution diluted with water, kept in the refrigerator overnight and filtered. The residue (m.p. > 300°) being insufficient for elemental analysis was rejected and the filtrate was acidified with glacial acetic acid when solid separated out. It was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from methanol to afford XVII as colourless prisms (1.1 g.; 50%), m.p. 205°–206°. (lit.⁹ m.p. 205°–206°). ν_{\max} (KBr) 765, 1065, 1270, 1345, 1450, 1640 (> C = N; > C = O), 1700 (> C = O at C₍₂₎), 1730 (> C = O at C₍₄₎) and 3190 cm⁻¹ (> NH; alcoholic OH), λ_{\max} (EtOH), 244, 310 nm. (ϵ_{\max} , 8800, 3960) (Found: C, 59.7; H, 5.3; N, 12.8. C₁₁H₁₂N₂O₃ requires: C, 60.0; H, 5.5; N, 12.7%).

2,3-Dihydro-2-methyloxazolo(2,3-b)quinazoline-5(4H)-one (XVI): (a) A solution of XIII (2.83 g.; 0.01 mole) in dry acetone (40 ml.) was refluxed with K₂CO₃ (3.5 g.) for 4 hr., filtered, concentrated and poured in crushed ice when white solid separated out. It was filtered, washed with water, dried and crystallised from ethyl acetate-light petroleum to yield XX as colourless needles (1.52 g.; 75%), m.p. 132°–133° (lit.⁹ m.p. 136°), ν_{\max} (KBr) 695, 765, 820, 1050, 1260, 1400, 1600, 1635, 1685 cm⁻¹. λ_{\max} (EtOH) 225, 252, 300, 325 nm. (ϵ_{\max} 36506, 7020, 3550, 2730) (Found: C, 64.9; H, 4.7; N, 14.0. C₁₁H₁₀N₂O₂ requires: C, 65.3; H, 5.0; N, 13.9%).

(b) XIV (1 g.) was refluxed with Ac₂O (5 ml.) for 15 min. and poured in crushed ice when white solid

separated out. It was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from ethyl acetate-light petroleum to give XVI as prismatic needles, m.p. and m.m.p. 131°-132°.

2-Methyloxazolo (2,3-b) quinazoline-5 (4H)-one (I; R = 2-CH₃): (a) XV (3.62 g.; 0.01 mole) was heated under reflux with a solution of KOH (2.8 g.; 0.05 mole) in ethanol (50 ml.) for 4 hr. Excess of ethanol (40 ml.) was distilled off, the residual solution was diluted with water and cooled in ice. The silky colourless needles that separated were filtered, washed with water, dried and crystallised from dilute ethanol to afford silky needles (0.56 g.) of a bromine containing compound (m.p. 170°-174°) identified as 2,3-dihydro-2-bromomethyloxazolo (2,3-b) quinazolin-5 (4H)-one (XVII). ν_{\max} (KBr) 770, 845, 1135, 1245, 1375, 1470 (aromatic), 1615 (> C = N-), 1690 cm⁻¹ (quinazoline > C = O). λ_{\max} (EtOH) 232 nm. (ϵ_{\max} 23227) (Found: C, 46.7; H, 3.0; N, 9.8; Br, 28.2. C₁₁H₉N₂O₂Br requires: C, 46.9; H, 3.2; N, 9.9; Br, 28.4%). Extraction of the filtrate with washings from ether (20 ml. x 3) however deposited bromine free white solid after the solvent was distilled off. This was crystallised from ether to furnish I (R = 2, -CH₃) as colourless needles (0.9 g.; 45%), m.p. 147°-148°. ν_{\max} (KBr) 760, 1190, 1270, 1325, 1410 (-CH₃), 1650, 1710, 3250 cm⁻¹. λ_{\max} (EtOH) 230, 240 nm. (ϵ_{\max} 8548) 310 nm (ϵ_{\max} 4199) (Found: C, 65.8; H, 3.9; N, 13.8. C₁₁H₉N₂O₂ requires: C, 66.0; H, 4.0; N, 14.0%).

(b) A mixture of XVI (0.5 g.), diphenylether (10 ml.) and palladised charcoal (1%; 0.1 g.) was heated under reflux for 12 hr., filtered hot and the filtrate was steam distilled to remove the solvent. The solid residue on purification by chromatography by its benzene solution over Brockmann's alumina and subsequent recrystallisation from ether gave I (R = 2-CH₃) as colourless needles (0.09 g.), m.p. and m.m.p. 146°-147°.

Ethyl-3-allylquinazoline-4 (3H)-one-2-oxyacetate (X): XII (11.1 g.; 0.055 mole) was dissolved in a dry methanolic solution of sodium methoxide (prepared from 50 ml. dry MeOH and 1.15 g. Na), cooled, the solvent distilled off and dried in an exicator. The residual dry solid (1.12 g.; 0.005 mole) in DMF (10 ml.) was treated with shaking ethyl bromoacetate (0.55 ml.; 0.005 mole), the clear reaction mixture warmed on steam bath for 2 hr., cooled and diluted with cold water, when white solid separated out. It was collected, washed with water and crystallised from MeOH to give (X) as colourless felted needles (1.0 g.; 69.4%), m.p. 95°-96°. ν_{\max} (KBr) 760, 940, 1245, 1500, 1650 (> N-C = O), 1605, 1710 (CO, ester), 1745, 2940 cm⁻¹. (Found: C, 62.9; H, 5.2; N, 10.0. C₁₅H₁₆N₂O₄ requires: C, 62.5; H, 5.5; N, 9.7%).

4-Allyl-1H, 2H-oxazolo (3,2-a) quinazoline-1,5 (4H)-dione (XIX): The ester (0.72 g.; 0.0025 mole) in

THF (5 ml.) was treated with KBH₄ (0.5 g.), dissolved in water (5 ml.) with a drop of 10% aq. NaOH and the homogeneous solution was kept overnight at the room temperature, when THF evaporated off. The residual solution was diluted with ice cold water and filtered from traces of insoluble material. The filtrate was cooled and acidified with 6N HCl when white precipitate separated out. It was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from MeOH to afford (XIX) as colourless needles (0.4 g.; 65.5%), m.p. 183°-184°. ν_{\max} (KBr) 760, 1255, 1340, 1440, 1640 (broad; tert. amide > C = O), 1710 (lactum; > C = O), 3105 cm⁻¹. (Found: C, 63.5; H, 4.7; N, 11.3. C₁₃H₁₂O₃N₂ requires: C, 63.9; H, 4.9; N, 11.5%).

2,3-Dihydro-2-methyloxazolo(3,2-c) quinazoline-5(4H)-one (XVIII): The dione (XII) (4.04 g.; 0.02 mole) was thoroughly mixed in heated PPA (15 ml) at 80° and heated at 150° for 0.5 hr. with occasional mixing. It was poured in ice water and left overnight. The solid separated was collected, washed with water and crystallised from ethyl acetate-light petroleum to give (XVIII) as colourless needles (2.4 g.; 60%), m.p. 202°-203°. ν_{\max} (KBr) 760, 1060, 1440, 1480, 1640, 1700, 3250 cm⁻¹. (Found: C, 65.0; H, 5.2; N, 14.1. C₁₁H₁₀N₂O₂ requires: C, 65.3; H, 5.0; N, 13.9%).

References

1. S. K. P. SINHA and D. N. CHAUDHURY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **47**, 1096; 1969, **46**, 31.
2. S. K. P. SINHA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1971, **48**, 432.
3. V. J. SHRIVASTAVA and D. N. CHAUDHURY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46**, 651.
4. (a) S. K. P. SINHA and B. D. SINGH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1971, **48**, 743.
(b) S. K. P. SINHA and M. P. THAKUR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **49**, 1185.
5. K. D. KAUFMANN and L. R. WORDEN, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1971, **26**, 117 and later papers.
6. T. N. GHOSH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, **7**, 981.
7. P. N. BHARGAVA and G. C. SINGH, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1967, **30**, 158.
8. W. L. F. ARMAREGO; Fused Pyrimidines. Part I, Quinazolines (Interscience Publishers), New York, 1967, 129.
9. M. S. PUAR, H. S. SACHDEVA and N. K. RAJAN, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1964, **2**, 285.
10. R. J. GROUT and M. W. PARTRIDGE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 3551.
11. K. D. KAUFMANN and W. E. RUSSEY, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1962, **27**, 670.
12. R. ADAMS and R. E. RINDFUSZ, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, **41**, 648.
13. N. A. LANGE and F. E. SHEIBBY, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, **53**, 3867, 1933, **55**, 1188; F. H. S. CURD, J. K. LANDQUIST and F. L. ROSE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 775.
14. W. L. F. Armarego: Fused Pyrimidines, Part I; Quinazolines (Interscience Publishers), New York, 1967, 129, 282.
15. S. K. P. Sinha and M. P. Thakur, Part IX (Communicated).